

First report of the presence of microplastics in bovine and porcine livers from Costa Rica

Primer reporte de la presencia de microplásticos en hígados de bovinos y porcinos de Costa Rica

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Abstract

[Objective] Given the ease with which microplastics (MP) are transported, ecosystems around the world are being polluted with these molecules. The reports of the presence of MP in marine organisms is alarming, but research on the terrestrial environment is still very scarce in Costa Rica; even more so in the Central American region. Given this, a multidisciplinary investigation was considered urgent to generate information, in this case, about contamination of animal tissues destined for human consumption. **[Methodology]** Whole livers, 20 from bovines and 18 swine's, were purchased from local markets from 4 of the main production meat regions in the country. **[Results]** Ninety percent of the bovine livers were positive for the presence of MP, while 83.3% of the porcine livers were. Fibers and films, ranging from 220 μm to 4.5 mm, most of them bluish green in color were found. **[Conclusions]** These characteristics can guide us towards the type of MP we are dealing with, but it is not possible to determine the exact origin of the particles and how they are reaching the livers of the animals. Truth is, these pollutants are reaching the human and animal population and since adverse effects have already been reported due to the presence of these particles in the human body, these results must be taken into account by healthcare professionals for any emerging diseases.

Key words: microplastics, bovine, porcine, liver.

Resumen

[Objetivo] Dada la facilidad con la que se distribuyen los microplásticos (MP), los ecosistemas de todo el mundo se están contaminando con estas partículas. Los reportes de la presencia de MP en organismos marinos son alarmantes, pero la investigación en el medio terrestre es muy escasa en Costa Rica; más aún en la región centroamericana. Ante esto, se consideró urgente una investigación multidisciplinaria para generar información, en este caso, sobre la contaminación de tejidos animales destinados al consumo humano. **[Metodología]** Se compraron hígados enteros, 20 de bovinos y 18 de cerdos, en mercados locales de las principales regiones productoras de carne del país. **[Resultados]** El 90% de los hígados bovinos fueron positivos para la presencia de MP, mientras que el 83,3% de

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los hígados de porcinos resultaron positivos. Se encontraron fibras y películas, en un rango de 220 µm a 4.5 mm, la mayoría de ellas de color verde azulado. **[Conclusiones]** Estas características nos pueden orientar hacia el tipo de MP al que nos enfrentamos, pero no es posible determinar el origen exacto de las partículas y cómo están llegando al hígado de los animales. Lo cierto es que estos contaminantes están llegando a la población humana y animal, y dado que ya se han reportado efectos adversos por la presencia de estas partículas en el cuerpo humano, estos resultados deben ser tenidos en cuenta por los profesionales de la salud ante cualquier enfermedad emergente.

Palabras clave: microplástico, bovino, porcino, hígado.

Introduction

It is already known that contamination by microplastics (MP) is an environmental problem that is affecting all ecosystems around the world (Cox et al., 2019), from the great depths of marine environments to the polar areas and the coast of all continents (Blumenröder et al., 2017), including freshwater and terrestrial systems (Horton et al., 2017; Blettler et al., 2018; Dris et al., 2018; Ramachandraiah et al., 2022). This is reinforced by the fact that in 2019, it was determined that MP are traveling by means of water condensation and are deposited as rain in remote places, even the ones uninhabited by humans (Allen et al., 2019).

The growing number of publications evidencing the presence of MP in marine organisms is alarming, contrary to research on the terrestrial environment, which is still very scarce. Nevertheless, given that Horton et al (2017) have shown that the number of plastics released to the terrestrial environment is 4 to 23 times greater than the amount released to the marine environment. At this time, despite the abundance and the potential to cause deleterious biological effects, studies related to the impact of MP in terrestrial organisms are limited. Although there are already reports of MP found in milk, meat, feed, blood (Van der Veen et al., 2022), earthworms and chickens for human consumption (Huerta-Lwanga, et al., 2017).

The Central American region is far behind in this regard, for now there are only a few reports of MP in marine environments (Davidson, 2012; Delvalle de Borrero et al., 2020; Kutralam-Muniasamy et al., 2020; Mazariegos-Ortíz et al., 2020; Fallon & Freeman, 2021; Oldenburg et al., 2021; Aldana Aranda et al., 2022; Orona-Návar et al., 2022); and other articles demonstrated the lack of literature in the region (Ivar Do Sul & Costa, 2014). The first report in Costa Rica was in 2018, since then, five other reports were made (Johnson et al., 2018; Bermúdez-Guzmán et al., 2020, Astorga et al., 2022a, Astorga et al., 2022b, Rojas-Jimenez et al., 2022). This information generated so far has primarily focused on marine organisms, highlighting a significant gap in our understanding of terrestrial ecosystems, making it a critical area of study. Therefore, studies on terrestrial animals, especially those consumed by humans, are essential to broaden our knowledge and address this public health concern in the country.

The liver, an organ through which blood from the stomach and intestine passes, has already been determined to be one of the routes through which microplastics are disseminated in the body (Osman et al., 2023; Kalra et al., 2024). In Costa Rica, the bovine and pork liver is widely consumed, with bovine liver typically prepared as steak and pork liver often made into pâté (Araya et al., 2014; Madrigal-Meneses & Caravaca-Rodríguez, 2020). This underscores the importance of understanding the potential health implications of contaminants in this filter organ by human consumers. Given this, the objective of the study

was to determine whether the Costa Rican population is consuming microplastics from terrestrial animals that are part of the human diet.

Materials and methods

- *Samples*

For this study bovine and porcine livers were obtained from butcher shops located in the center of cities. This implies that they were healthy organs that had successfully passed the veterinary inspection at the slaughterhouse. The livers were randomly collected, bought as a whole and not sliced, as it is customary to sell to the public. A total of 20 bovine livers and 18 porcine livers were processed, distributed in the regions of greatest meat production, to have a representative sample of both types of liver (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of sample points in the regions of greatest meat production in Costa Rica. Green points are bovine samples, and blue points are porcine samples.

- *Tissue processing*

To prevent the potential contamination from external sources, such as air-borne fibers, the laboratory workspace was frequently cleaned, and work was performed in a laminar airflow cabinet, particularly for preparing solutions, sieving and filtration, when possible. In addition, glassware was washed thoroughly, oven-dried and covered with aluminum foil when not in use (Astorga et al., 2022b).

For chemical digestion, a sample of 100 grams was taken from the inside of each liver, taking into consideration the central axis of the organ to ensure that the sample showed part of the hepatic veins and arteries. To extract the MPs from liver samples, the tissue was chemically digested following the method described by Cole et al (2014), Kühn et al (2017), and Bessa et al (2019). A solution of 10% KOH to digest the organic matter was added. The volume of the liquid did not exceed 50% of the total volume of the Erlenmeyer (250 or 500 ml). To obtain a dissolved solution, Erlenmeyers were covered with aluminum and placed in an oscillating incubator at 60°C at 300 rpm for 24 h. Subsequently, the digested content from the chemical process was sieved through a 60 µ stainless steel sieve and transferred to a clean glass Petri dish. The excess of water was evaporated in an oven at 45 °C for 30 h. Glass Petri dishes were covered with aluminum foil with small holes to allow water to evaporate and prevent possible airborne plastic contamination (Enders et al., 2020).

- *Identification and validation of microplastic*

All particles were identified, measured, and photographed using a stereo microscope OPTIKA SZ-ST2 with image analysis system AMSCOPE MU1000 Camera with AMPSCOPE software. Plastic particles <5000 µm were classified as MPs (Andrady 2011); they were also classified by type as: fibers (elongated), fragments (irregular pieces), pellets or films (thin) and categorized by their color (Hidalgo-Ruz et al., 2012; Qiu et al., 2016; Martin et al., 2017; Enders et al., 2020).

Results

Out of the 20 bovine livers processed, 90% (n= 18) were positive for the presence of MP. All the particles found were classified as fibers with an average size of 1530 µm (range 230 µm to 3680 µm) and most of them (38.10%) bluish green in color. Other colors of the fibers detected were black (21.43%), blue (16.67%), purple (7.14%), red (7.14%), white translucent (4.76%), brown (2.38%) and sky blue (2.38%) (figure 2, 3). The amount of MP per gram of liver tissue processed varied from 0.009 to 0.074 with an average of 0.0203 MP g-1 (figure 4).

On the other hand, of the 18 processed porcine livers, 83.3% (n= 15) were positive for the presence of MP. Ninety-five (98.96%) of the particles found were classified as fibers with an average size of 1240 µm (range 220 µm - 4510 µm) and most of them (32.29%) bluish green in color. Other colors of the fibers detected were red (22.92%), blue (15.63%), white translucent (11.46%), black (9.38%), green (5.21%), and purple (3.13%) (figure 2, 3). The other particle found was classified as a film, color red, with a size of 2150 µm. The amount of MP per gram of liver tissue processed varied from 0.013 to 0.2948 with an average of 0.063 MP g-1 (figure 4).

Figure 2. Percentage distribution of colors found in bovine and porcine livers.

Figure 3. Microplastic particles found in bovine (A) and porcine (B) livers from the regions of greatest meat production of Costa Rica.

Figure 4. Average of microplastics (MP per gram of tissue) found in bovine and porcine livers.

Discussion

Due to the ubiquity of MP, living organisms are inevitably taking them through ingestion or inhalation (Galloway et al., 2017). Since the objective of the study was investigating if the Costa Rican population is consuming MP in products of animal origin, without attempting to compare the quantity of microplastics between regions or trace the origin of the microplastics, there is no information on the specific food supplied to each of the animals whose livers were sampled. However, in Costa Rica most bovines are on a diet based on grazing with concentrate supplementation based mostly on corn, soybean meal and sugarcane molasses. While most pigs are kept housed on a diet based on fattening concentrated feed based mostly on corn and soybean meal (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 2022).

The presence of MP has been documented in salt (Yang et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2018), soybean meal (Walkinshaw et al., 2022), sugarcane (Liebezeit & Liebezeit 2013) and corn (Haluska, 2020; Garrido & Costanzo 2022; Shi et al., 2023); ingredients often used in the animal feed industry. Also, MP of marine origin could be incorporated into foods of terrestrial animals due to the use of derivatives of fish in the manufacture of feed concentrates (Bouwmeester et al., 2015; Walkinshaw et al., 2022). Another possible route of contamination would be drinking water, in a systematic study carried out by Danopoulos et al (2020), it is mentioned that microplastics are ubiquitous and the studies confirmed the presence of microplastics in drinking water.

The results of our study show the presence of microplastics (MP) in liver samples intended for human consumption. Although cross-contamination during processing, from the slaughter of the animals to their subsequent market commercialization in the country, cannot be ruled out (Garrido & Costanzo, 2022), this is considered unlikely. Extensive precautions were taken to process the samples carefully, including taking the digestion sample from inside the organ and implementing all possible measures to avoid contamination in the

laboratory. Regardless of the contamination source, our study aimed to determine the presence of microplastics in the product that ultimately reaches the consumer.

In this study, the amount of MP per gram found in animal livers (bovine: average 0.024 MP g⁻¹; porcine average 0.074 MP g⁻¹) is lower than that found in human livers, where in healthy humans their livers were found to have a number of plastic particles ranging from 0 to 2.2 per gram of tissue (average of 1 MP g⁻¹), while patients with liver disease (cirrhosis) the number increased 8 times (average of 8.3 MP g⁻¹) (Hovartis et al., 2022).

In our studies, the size of the MP found was bigger in both; bovine (average 1530 µm) and porcine (average 1240 µm) livers than the size of the particles found in cirrhotic human liver tissue, which ranged from 3.0 to 29.5 µm (average 9.8 µm); however, they could not determine whether the accumulation of MP is the cause or the consequence of liver disease in human subjects (Hovartis et al., 2022). Still, MP has been reported to damage liver cells, alter fat metabolism, and enzyme activities in crabs, fishes and mice (Lu et al., 2016; Deng et al., 2017, Lu et al., 2018; Chae et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2018).

While scientific literature reports translocation of MP ranging from 1 to 500 µm into different tissues (liver, cell membranes, the blood-brain barrier and even the placenta) of several species (Hussain et al., 2001; Vethaak & Leslie 2016; Triebkorn et al., 2019; Elizalde-Velazquez et al., 2020; Yee, et al., 2021) causing oxidative stress, cell damage and inflammation; some authors have recently challenged whether microplastics are capable of translocating (Schür et al., 2019). Currently, the disagreement is related to the size of particles that can be taken up by cells and translocated among tissues (Triebkorn et al., 2019).

Haave et al (2021) carried out a study between 2017 and 2019 on wild animals (mammals, birds and fishes), and found MP in the liver of anchovies. It is mentioned that there was a translocation of MP to the tissues of the animals studied, as the MP that crosses the epithelial tissue of the digestive tract could then be transported through the portal system to the liver (Garrido & Costanzo, 2022).

Based on the criteria for visual identification of microplastics described by Zhang et al (2020), it is that the information regarding the shape, size, and color of the MP found provides us important information for identifying the type of plastic we are dealing with, but not about their origin and how our animals may be contaminating. In the case of shapes: fibers in the urban areas have been linked to industrial activities; and flakes are attributed to mechanical and chemical degradation. Colors are due to pigments that are used in the fabrication of plastics. For example: black colored plastics have been shown to contain PU transparent plastics indicate polypropylene; opaque plastics point to LDPE; and white to polyethylene (Ramachandraiah et al., 2022).

Plastics are generally considered to be inert materials. However, among the damages that MP could cause in the body, the following have been proposed: vascular embolization, inflammatory responses (associated with cell phagocytosis of particles and increased autoimmune response) (Wright & Kelly, 2017; Yee et al., 2021; Hu et al., 2023), gastrointestinal alterations such as dysbiosis and altered mucus secretion (Garrido & Costanzo, 2022), cytotoxicity due to oxidative stress mechanisms (Schirinzi et al., 2017; Solomando, et al., 2020), liver damage (Garrido & Costanzo, 2022), alterations in energy and lipid metabolism (Deng et al., 2017), and neurotoxicity (Garrido & Costanzo, 2022).

In some plastics, additives (such as bromates as flame retardants, plasticizers such as phthalates, and heat stabilizing metal compounds) may constitute a major fraction of their composition; and the toxicity of a large part of the additives is well known. Some well-

documented examples in humans include reproductive toxicity (eg, bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate [DEHP] and bisphenol A [BPA]), carcinogenicity (vinyl chloride and butadiene), and mutagenicity (benzene and phenol) (Campanale et al., 2020). In addition to additives, MP can release residual monomers and degradation products that have formed on the surface by chemical or photochemical reactions during their stay in the environment (Lucas et al., 2008, Ramachandraiah et al., 2022). Studies of the chemical composition of plastic in field samples are scarce due to the high cost of the tests; but they are necessary to understand the toxicity of these particles.

Finally, these species studied, as products consumed by humans, could increase the human consumptions of MP, as other studies have exposed. Yee et al (2021) indicated that the human food chain is a major source of MP consumption, they reviewed MP pollution in food (seafood, sugar, honey, salt, alcohol, bottled water, tap water and air), and now we have evidence of MP in terrestrial animals of human consumption.

Conclusions

Although it cannot be determined the origin of these MPs in the livers, the truth is that this is reaching the human population that consumes them. The significance of this research at the local and regional levels lies in several key aspects. Firstly, identifying microplastics in human-consumed livers provides crucial data, hedding light on environmental contamination, thus informing public awareness about food safety. This work does not intend to make the population stop consuming these products, but these results must be considered by healthcare professionals as it is already reported that the presence of these particles in tissues can trigger adverse reactions in the digestive and respiratory systems, skin reactions, reproductive problems, among many others. Secondly, it underscores the environmental impact, emphasizing the interaction between plastic pollution and the food chain, which could spur initiatives to mitigate plastic contamination and safeguard local natural resources. Thirdly, the findings may influence policy-making and regulations, leading to stricter measures in waste management and food safety practices, thereby benefiting public health and the environment locally and regionally. Lastly, this pioneering study opens avenues for further research into microplastic presence and impacts on other organs and food species, thereby advancing global understanding of this issue.

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Conflict of interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Author contribution statement

All the authors declare that the final version of this paper was read and approved. The total contribution percentage for the conceptualization, preparation, and correction of this paper was as follows: N.S.B, K.U.N, C.V.M. & A.G.R: 100%.

Data availability statement

The data supporting the results of this study will be made available by the corresponding author, [A.G.R.], upon reasonable request.

Preprint

Una versión Preprint de este artículo fue depositada en: [Agregar el enlace](#)

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